

Defect Engineering Stabilized AgSbTe₂ with High Thermoelectric Performance

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Abstract

Thermoelectric (TE) generators enable the direct and reversible conversion between heat and electricity, providing applications in both refrigeration and power generation. The grand challenge in the field is related to the low conversion efficiency of TE devices. In the last decade, several TE materials with relatively high figures of merit (zT) have been reported in low- and high-temperature regimes. However, there is an urgent demand for high-performance TE materials working in the mid-temperature range (400-700 K). Herein, p-type AgSbTe₂ materials stabilized with S and Se co-doping are demonstrated to exhibit an outstanding maximum figure of merit (zT_{\max}) of 2.3 at 673 K and an average figure of merit (zT_{ave}) of 1.59 over the wide temperature range of 300 - 673 K. This exceptional performance arises from an enhanced carrier density resulting from a higher concentration of silver vacancies, a vastly improved Seebeck coefficient enabled by the flattening of the valence band maximum and the inhibited formation of n-type Ag₂Te, and a highly improved stability beyond 673 K. The optimized material is used to fabricate a single-leg device with efficiencies of up to 13.7% at a temperature difference of 400 K, and an uncouple TE device reaching energy conversion efficiencies up to 12.3% at a temperature difference of 370 K. These results highlight an effective strategy to engineer high-performance TE material for cost-effective waste heat recovery in the mid-temperature range.

1. Introduction

Thermoelectric (TE) devices provide reliable solutions for power generation from waste-heat, precise temperature control and miniaturized cooling. The TE generator (TEG) market is foreseen to grow at a compound annual growth rate above 10% in this decade. However, this projection relies on the continued development of high-performance materials and their adoption in commercial TE devices.

The performance of a TE material is determined by a dimensionless figure of merit, $zT = (S^2\sigma/\kappa)T$, where S , σ , κ and T are the Seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity, thermal conductivity and absolute temperature, respectively^{1,2}. Using the material's figure of merit, the energy conversion efficiency (η) of a TEG under a temperature gradient ($\Delta T = T_h - T_c$) can be estimated from the average zT (zT_{ave}) over the entire temperature range as: $\eta = \frac{T_h - T_c}{T_h} \cdot$

$$\frac{\sqrt{1+zT_{\text{ave}}}-1}{\sqrt{1+zT_{\text{ave}}+T_c/T_h}} \quad 3-5$$

In the last two decades, the TE field has experienced significant progress, with several breakthrough materials reaching $zT > 2$, such as SnSe⁶⁻⁹, PbTe^{10,11}, and Cu_{2-x}Se^{12,13}. However, the peak performance of these materials is typically achieved above 700 K. Previous research

works has proven that Bi_2Te_3 and Mg_3Bi_2 possesses excellent TE properties near room temperature (RT). Recently, Ag_2Se exhibited great potential as a n-type TE material around RT owing to its inherently low thermal conductivity and narrow band gap (~ 0.2 eV).¹⁴⁻¹⁶ However, there is a distinct lack of high-performance TE materials working in the mid-temperature range, between 400 and 700 K. Indeed, most of the waste heat produced either from industrial sectors or automobiles is in the temperature range of 400–900 K.^{17,18} Therefore, developing high-performance mid-temperature TE materials is of significant practical value.

Recently, AgSbTe_2 has emerged as a promising TE material for lower-medium temperature power generation applications. AgSbTe_2 is a p-type TE material characterized by intrinsically very low thermal conductivities ($0.6\text{-}0.7$ $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) and large Seebeck coefficients (> 300 $\mu\text{V K}^{-1}$), thus showing high potential for middle-temperature TE applications.¹⁹⁻²³ Polycrystalline AgSbTe_2 demonstrates particularly good TE properties when alloyed with PbTe ¹⁰ and GeTe ²⁴. Besides, Cd doping in AgSbTe_2 achieved an ultrahigh TE performance with the spontaneous formation of nanoscale superstructures.²⁰ At room temperature, AgSbTe_2 has a rocksalt structure, where Ag/Sb are randomly distributed on the cation sublattice, and Te occupies the anion sites. However, the phase diagram of Sb_2Te_3 - Ag_2Te reveals that stoichiometric AgSbTe_2 is thermodynamically unstable at temperatures below 633 K, where it tends to decompose to Ag_2Te and Sb_2Te_3 .^{25, 26} Previous studies consistently identified the precipitated Ag_2Te phase and other impurities coexisting within the AgSbTe_2 matrix regardless of the synthesis strategies applied.²⁷⁻³¹ Therefore, the precise nature of the AgSbTe_2 crystal structure and its stability are open debates.

Figure 1. Thermoelectric figure of merit and power generation performance. (A) zT values as a function of temperature for pristine and doped AgSbTe_2 . (B) Comparison of the maximum

conversion efficiency (η_{max}) as a function of temperature difference of doped p-type AgSbTe₂ uncouple device with that of other state-of-art uncouple/multi-couple devices.^{8, 32-40}

Here, we demonstrate the enhanced charge carrier density of p-type AgSbTe₂ using selenium and sulfur as effective dopants that collectively reduce the formation energy of silver vacancies and stabilize AgSbTe₂ by inhibiting the formation of n-type Ag₂Te. This compositional engineering enables a dramatic increase in zT from 0.6 (undoped) to 2.3 at 673 K (Figure 1A). This high-performance material is used to fabricate single-leg and uncouple TE devices with energy conversion efficiencies of up to 13.7 % and 12.3%, respectively (Figure 1B).

2. Result and Discussion

Polycrystalline AgSbTe₂ was synthesized by melting a mixture of the stoichiometric elements, grinding the obtained ingots and re-consolidating the material by spark plasma sintering (see the experimental section in SI). As shown by high-resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy (HR-STEM) images and the double diffraction spots of the fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis, nanoprecipitates of the monoclinic Ag₂Te phase, with an average size of ~17 nm, were formed within the polycrystalline AgSbTe₂ (Figure 2A, S1H, S4E). This finding agrees with Park et al.'s work which observed Ag₂Te nano-precipitations with a size of about 10 nm distributed inside the AgSbTe₂ matrix.²²

At the same time, a high density of line defects was also detected in AgSbTe₂ (Figure S2, S3). Interestingly, FFT analysis indicates that grains that contain multiple line defects are composed of the same face-centered cubic AgSbTe₂ phase, indicating that the line defects can be produced by Ag₂Te phase transition when cooling down during the synthesis. Complementary X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were unequivocally indexed to the face-centered-cubic (fcc) AgSbTe₂ structure, while a series of weak diffraction peaks were associated with the presence of the monoclinic Ag₂Te, confirming the coexistence of both phases (Figure 2C, S4E).

The appearance of Ag₂Te precipitation is a consequence of AgSbTe₂ decomposition due to its unstable nature. Given that Ag₂Te is an n-type semiconductor and presents structural phase transition at ~425 K, a small amount of Ag₂Te can negatively impact the electronic transport properties of p-type AgSbTe₂.⁴¹ Thus, suppressing the formation of Ag₂Te impurities is critical to optimize the AgSbTe₂ TE performance. The crystal orbital Hamiltonian population analysis demonstrates that the instability of AgSbTe₂ comes from the antibonding states beneath the Fermi level, where the strong hybridization of Sb-5s and Te-5p states push Te-5p antibonding states toward the frontier of valence bands,⁴⁴ which is further confirmed by the density of states

(DOS, Figure S6). Therefore, p-type doping, by removing electrons contributing to the antibonding states, can make the AgSbTe_2 system more stable.

Figure 2. Stabilized AgSbTe_2 phase without Ag_2Te precipitation. HR-STEM images, FFT patterns, and crystallographic maps of pristine AgSbTe_2 (A) and $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.1}\text{S}_{0.05}$ (B). The

crystallographic maps were obtained from the green- and red-circled diffraction spots, corresponding to the fcc AgSbTe₂ and monoclinic Ag₂Te phases, respectively. (C) XRD patterns of as-synthesized AgSbTe_{2-x-y}Se_xS_y pellets. (D) Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) curves of AgSbTe₂ (black line), AgSbTe_{1.85}Se_{0.15} (blue line), and AgSbTe_{1.85}Se_{0.1}S_{0.05} (red line). Hall charge carrier transport properties: carrier concentration (E) and mobility (F).

Herein, we stabilized the AgSbTe₂ matrix by introducing small amounts of Se and S within the anion sublattice, facilitating the formation of cation vacancies as p-type carriers. As shown by XRD analysis, the doped material displayed cubic AgSbTe₂ as the unique phase (Figure 2C), with no evidence of the presence of Ag₂Te. Besides, the XRD peaks shifted to higher angles (Figure S4) upon introducing Se/S, due to the larger ion radius of Te²⁻ (2.21 Å) in comparison to S²⁻ (1.84 Å) and Se²⁻ (1.98 Å), demonstrating the successful substitution of Te by Se/S. Line defects were not observed after doping. Further, a longer-range crystallographic order was identified by HR-STEM and FFT analysis (Figure 2B, S5) confirming the pure AgSbTe₂ phase. Additional confirmation of the inhibited formation of Ag₂Te was obtained by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis that showed the suppression of the endothermic peak at 423 K associated with the α -Ag₂Te to β -Ag₂Te phase transition (Figure 2D).⁴²

To gain more insight into the effect of Se and S doping on AgSbTe₂ structure, we determined the formation energies of the individual and complex defects using density functional theory (DFT) calculations. Defect calculations were carried out adopting the $Fd\bar{3}m$ conventional cell as the initial structure, which presents the lowest formation enthalpy among AgSbTe₂ crystal structures.^{45,46} Due to the antibonding contributions on the top of the valence band, AgSbTe₂ tends to generate a high density of intrinsic acceptor dopants, such as Ag vacancies (V_{Ag}), to ease its inherent structural instability.⁴⁴ Owing to the charge compensation mechanism, defect complexes that include a positively charged Sb substitution at an Ag site (Sb_{Ag}) spontaneously form to maintain charge neutrality.⁴³ This compensation effect will consequently lead to an overall low net concentration of holes. Indeed, pristine AgSbTe₂ is characterized by a hole concentration of $1.2 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at room temperature (Figure 2E, Table S4), well below that required for TE application. As such, optimizing the hole carrier densities in AgSbTe₂ system is of vital importance.

Figure 3. DFT-calculated defect formation energy, electronic structure, and Seebeck coefficients. (A and B) Defect formation energies of individual defects V_{Ag} , Sb_{Ag} and complex defects $V_{Ag}^- + Sb_{Ag}^+$ and $2V_{Ag}^- + Sb_{Ag}^{2+}$ with respect to the Fermi level in AgSbTe₂ (A) and AgSbTe_{2-x-y}Se_xS_y (B). (C and D) Band structure of AgSbTe₂ (C) and AgSbTe_{1.82}Se_{0.12}S_{0.06} (D). (E and F) Calculated Seebeck coefficient as a function of temperature in AgSbTe₂ (E) and AgSbTe_{1.82}Se_{0.12}S_{0.06} (F), considering hole concentrations in the range from $5 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Experiment data is plotted using black dots.

Figure 3 displays the formation energies of each possible defect in AgSbTe₂ and AgSbTe_{2-x-y}Se_xS_y under Ag-rich (AgSbTe₂-Ag₂Te) and Ag-poor (AgSbTe₂-Sb₂Te₃) conditions. As to individual defects, V_{Ag} in pristine AgSbTe₂ exhibits significantly lower formation energy than

Sb_{Ag} (Figure 3A), which is consistent with the previous report.⁴³ Meanwhile, the formation energy of V_{Ag} after Se and S doping is further decreased (Figure 3B), whereas that of Sb_{Ag} is increased, suggesting a much more favorable formation of V_{Ag} . In particular, V_{Ag} behaves as a single acceptor and is strongly preferred to stabilize AgSbTe₂ by suppressing the antibonding states. As to complex defects, DFT calculation reveals that $(2V_{Ag}^- + Sb_{Ag}^{2+})$ systematically presents lower binding energy than $(V_{Ag}^- + Sb_{Ag}^+)$, implying that Sb_{Ag} tends to be double charged within the complex, while a 1+ or 0 charge is favored in single Sb_{Ag} defect. The calculated binding energy of $(2V_{Ag}^- + Sb_{Ag}^{2+})$, $E_b(2V_{Ag}^- + Sb_{Ag}^{2+})$ (defined in SI), in AgSbTe₂ and AgSbTe_{2-x-y}Se_xS_y is -0.169 eV and +0.164 eV, respectively. Thus, while pristine AgSbTe₂ tends to generate complex defects over multiple independent defects, the positive $E_b(2V_{Ag}^- + Sb_{Ag}^{2+})$ suggests that individual defects are preferentially generated in AgSbTe_{2-x-y}Se_xS_y.

Compared with previously reported single Se-doping approach,^{21,23} S and Se co-doping leads to an additional decrease in formation energy of V_{Ag} (Figure S16). Considering that the formation energy of V_{Ag}^- is notably lower than Sb_{Ag}^{2+} , aforementioned results further conclude that Se and S doping results in a higher concentration of individual defect V_{Ag} . The stimulated larger quantities of V_{Ag} not only play a crucial role in stabilizing the AgSbTe₂ structure but also allows a finer tuning and thus optimization of the carrier concentration. This is corroborated by experimental data on the charge carrier density at both low (5-200K, Figure S25) and high temperature regions (300-570 K, Figure 2E). With the introduction of Se and S doping, the room-temperature carrier density increases to $2.4 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which is significantly higher than pristine and Se-doped AgSbTe₂ (Table S4), close to the optimal carrier concentration of Bi₂Te₃.^{32, 47} Meanwhile, both carrier concentration and carrier mobility (Figure 2F) exhibited minor variation over the full temperature range after doping, due to the elimination of the Ag₂Te phase. As expected, the hole mobility decreases with the introduction of dopants because of the presence of heavy holes and significantly improved effective mass, which will be discussed in the later section.

The optimized doping concentration, resulting in the highest electrical conductivity in the temperature range from 300 K to 673 K, was found at 15 mol% (Figure 4A). At near room temperature, σ increased from $\sim 89 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for pristine AgSbTe₂ to $\sim 244 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for AgSbTe_{1.85}Se_{0.1}S_{0.05}. For pristine AgSbTe₂, σ initially decreased and then increased with temperature as the bipolar contribution became dominant, i.e. at around 450 K, which is consistent with our DFT calculations. Although the introduction of Se and S resulted in a decrease of the Seebeck coefficient associated with the increase in charge carrier concentration,

high Seebeck coefficients over $\sim 230 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ across the entire temperature range were still measured for all the doped samples (Figure 4B). The doping effect on the electronic structure was further analyzed using DFT calculations. The electronic band structures of both AgSbTe_2 and $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.82}\text{Se}_{0.12}\text{S}_{0.06}$ shows pseudo-gap-like features that tend to underestimate the Seebeck coefficient^{20, 21, 48, 49} (Figure 3C, 3D). Thus, we adjusted the bandgap using the experimental value of 0.35 eV obtained by infrared spectroscopy (Figure S7, S8). With the introduction of dopants, the valence band maximum (VBM) of AgSbTe_2 is flattened at the Γ point (Figure 4C), together with a significant band splitting. The calculated effective mass of the valence band maximum indicates substantial heavier holes in doped $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.82}\text{Se}_{0.12}\text{S}_{0.06}$ (Figure 4D), indicating the enhancement of the Seebeck coefficient and subsequently the power factor.

Based on the calculated electronic band structure, a multiband model was used to further simulate the electronic transport data and particularly the Seebeck coefficient (Figure 3E, 3F). The temperature-dependent Seebeck coefficient plot demonstrated a good consistency between experimental data and the calculated values. In pristine AgSbTe_2 , both experimental data and DFT results displayed a decrease of the Seebeck coefficient at about 450 K associated with bipolar transport, which is typical of a narrow band gap semiconductor. Above this temperature, the growing influence of the thermally generated charge carriers also becomes evident in the increase of the electrical conductivity (Figure 4A) and the bipolar thermal conductivity (Figure 4F) experimentally obtained for AgSbTe_2 . At the same hole concentration, the band flattening calculated for $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.82}\text{Se}_{0.12}\text{S}_{0.06}$ results in significantly larger Seebeck coefficients than those obtained for AgSbTe_2 .

The combination of enhanced electrical conductivities and preserved high Seebeck coefficients in $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.15}\text{S}_{0.05}$ results in substantially larger PFs than pristine AgSbTe_2 over the entire temperature range (Figure 4E). The maximum PF for $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.15}\text{S}_{0.05}$ was obtained at 673 K and it reached $\sim 2.1 \text{ mW m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-2}$, which is comparable to the PFs obtained for state-of-the-art TE materials that are generally characterized by higher thermal conductivities, such as PbTe ⁵⁰, MgAgSb ⁵¹, and Cu_2Se ¹³. On top of the excellent PFs obtained here, $\text{AgSbTe}_{2-x-y}\text{Se}_x\text{S}_y$ was characterized by a very low thermal conductivity (Figure 4F). In pristine AgSbTe_2 , κ_{tot} initially decreased and then increased (starting at around 450 K) with temperature. The increase of thermal conductivity κ_{tot} at high temperatures was associated with the increase of the electronic component of the thermal conductivity κ_e and the contribution of the bipolar thermal conductivity κ_{bi} (Figure S11). Partial substitution of (Se+S) at the position of Te in AgSbTe_2 did not completely suppress bipolar effects, but significantly reduced the bipolar thermal

conductivity contribution, which is attributed to a combination of the higher hole carrier concentration and the increase of the bandgap thus shifting the thermal generation of charge carriers to higher temperatures. In addition to optimised carrier density, the other benefit of increased silver vacancies is low lattice thermal conductivity (κ_L). V_{Ag} represents a severe local disruption of the $AgSbTe_2$ lattice, making vacancy-phonon scattering a particularly strong form of point defect scattering. The inclusion of smaller S atoms also induces strong lattice distortion because of the mismatch of ionic mass, size, and bond strength caused by S atoms substitute on the Te sublattice. Overall, the doping induces drastic fluctuations in both mass and strain that notably strengthen the phonon scattering thus resulting in low κ_L . The existence of doping-induced lattice distortion was identified by the shrinking of the lattice parameter (Figure S4). Furthermore, the lattice softening is confirmed by reduction of sound velocity (v_s) in sample $AgSbTe_{1.85}Se_{0.1}S_{0.05}$ (Table S5). In addition, the drop of Debye temperature obtained from low temperature heat measurement provides extra evidence for significant lattice softening (Figure S26).

As a result of the enhanced carrier concentration and the high Seebeck coefficients maintained, outstanding zT values up to 2.3 and a zT_{ave} of 1.59 were realized within the temperature range 300-673 K. Besides, the production of materials with such high zT values was very reproducible as shown from the results obtained by analyzing samples obtained from different batches and measured for several heating-cooling cycles (Figure S12, S13). Additionally, to investigate the thermal stability of co-doped samples, we performed in situ high temperature XRD (Figure S14A), DSC analysis (Figure S14B), and long-term thermal treatment (Figure S15) on $AgSbTe_{1.85}Se_{0.1}S_{0.05}$ pellet. Compared with undoped $AgSbTe_2$, the results indicated that $AgSbTe_{1.85}Se_{0.1}S_{0.05}$ presents high thermal stability and reliable TE performance against thermal annealing, which is necessary for better maturing TE technology towards actual applications.

Figure 4. Thermoelectric properties of $\text{AgSbTe}_{2-x-y}\text{Se}_x\text{S}_y$ as a function of temperature. (A) Electrical conductivity (σ), (B) Seebeck coefficient (S), (C) schematic of the electronic band structure, (D) effective mass, (E) power factor (PF), (F) thermal conductivity (κ).

The next step towards demonstrating the potential of a TE material is the fabrication and testing of TE devices. To test TE efficiency, first, a $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.1}\text{S}_{0.05}$ single-leg module was assembled (Figure 5A). With a fixed cold side temperature of ~ 280 K, the open-circuit voltage V_{oc} increased linearly with ΔT , confirming the low contact resistance of the single-leg module. The maximum output power (P_{out}) of the device increased from ≈ 1 mW under $\Delta T = 45$ K, to 52 mW under $\Delta T = 400$ K. Accordingly, a power density up to 0.85 W/cm^2 was determined.

From these output power values, an energy conversion efficiency $\eta=13.7\%$ was achieved at a temperature difference of $\Delta T=400$ K, which is close (77 %) to the maximum theoretical value (17.7%). Besides, as evidenced by the measurement of three different single-leg modules, excellent experimental repeatability was obtained from device to device (Figure S18). Afterward, we fabricated a segmented unicouple module with leg length of 6.5 mm, which consisted of p-type $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.1}\text{S}_{0.05}/\text{Bi}_{0.4}\text{Sb}_{1.6}\text{Te}_3$ and n-type $\text{Yb}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{3.75}\text{Fe}_{0.25}\text{Sb}_{12}$ ⁵². We measured the open circuit voltage V_{oc} and device voltage V_d , calculated the internal resistance R_i , peak power output, power density and heat flow Q_{out} by varying hot-side temperature from 390 K to 673 K under nearly constant cold-side temperature of 298 K.

Figure 5. (A-C) TE single-leg module performance: the current dependent (A) output power and (B) conversion efficiency, (C) the conversion efficiency of three independent single-leg modules as a function of temperature gradient, insert with a schematic diagram of the setup used to test the power and conversion efficiency under vacuum. (D-F) TE unicouple device performance: the current dependent (D) maximum output power and (E) conversion efficiency, (F) cyclic test on the device after thermal cycling between 373 K and 673 K for a given number of cycles.

The output voltage (V_{oc}) as a function of ΔT was tested and is displayed in Figure S21 which increased linearly with ΔT , confirming the low contact resistance of the fabricated device. The

internal resistance (R_i) was determined to be 42.5 milliohms at room temperature and mildly decrease to 39.0 milliohms at 673 K, which is associated with the slightly reduced electrical resistivity of $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.1}\text{S}_{0.05}$ at higher temperatures (Figure S22-24). Overall, the maximum output power (P_{out}) of the device increased from ≈ 5.5 mW under $\Delta T = 92$ K, to 144.4 mW under $\Delta T = 370$ K (Figure 5D). Accordingly, a power density up to 0.79 W/cm² was determined. An outstanding device energy conversion efficiency of 12.3% was achieved at a temperature difference of $\Delta T = 370$ K (Figure 5F). Compared with the high conversion efficiency in the literature (Figure 1B), our $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.1}\text{S}_{0.05}$ -based module realized the highest value among the others (PbTe, GeTe, Skutterudite, and half-Heusler) across the mid-temperature range. The origin of this high conversion efficiency is found on the optimized zT over the whole temperature range. Besides, the TEG shows stable and reliable output performance under thermal cycling between 373 K and 673K up to 10 cycles.

4. Conclusion

To summarize, the charge carrier density and phase stability of polycrystalline AgSbTe_2 was optimized by doping with S and Se. The substitution of Te by S/Se enables decoupling the generation of V_{Ag} acceptor defects from the generation of Sb_{Ag} donors, leading to the stabilized AgSbTe_2 phase. Besides, the introduction of S and Se simultaneously flattened the VBM and inhibited the formation of n-type Ag_2Te , resulting in optimized electrical transport properties. Thus, $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.1}\text{S}_{0.05}$ alloys with high power factors up to $21 \mu\text{W cm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$ were obtained. Besides, S and Se doping also resulted in a decrease of the lattice thermal conductivity down to $0.31 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$. Overall, $\text{AgSbTe}_{1.85}\text{Se}_{0.1}\text{S}_{0.05}$ was characterized by a maximum $zT = 2.3$ at 673 K and a $zT_{ave} = 1.59$ over the temperature range 300 - 673 K, which outperforms most of the current state-of-the-art p-type materials in the middle-temperature range. We further experimentally engineered single-leg and uncouple modules with a minimized contact resistance that resulted in energy conversion efficiency of up to 13.7% and 12.3%, respectively. Overall, this work provides cutting-edge insight into engineering high-performance medium-temperature TE materials and devices for efficient waste heat recovery.

Supporting Information ((delete if not applicable))

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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